

PRINCIPLES OF NAMING IN ERGONOMICS AND TYPOLOGICAL
CLASSIFICATION

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A noun is a linguistic sign that names a separate object (personal noun) or any object from a general class (common or common noun). The naming of things has interested people since ancient times. Initially (until the 19th century), the theory of naming developed within the framework of philosophy. In ancient Greece, there were two different views about the relationship between the name of a word and the thing it named. One of them was to name things arbitrarily and by appointment. Supporters of the latter argued that each name is correct according to the nature of the thing⁸.

Platon believed that the problem of the origin of names cannot be solved in one way. In Plato's dialogue "Cratylus", two important aspects of naming are distinguished: 1) the relationship between the name and the name; 2) connection between a noun and an object. It examines two points: 1) who says it and 2) the truth of the naming. Thus, if the name is true, it is proved to be true; a name is correct if it accurately reflects the objective properties of the thing.

As Yu. V. Rozhdestvensky noted, Platon considered modeling, that is, the "image" of describing an object, to be the leading principle in the creation of names. Plato, the most general principles of modeling accepted in his time, is called folk etymology. According to the rules of folk etymology, names are divided into two categories: primary and derived. Derivatives are constructed from primaries⁹. Much modern theoretical work on onomastics is based on the ideas of the 19th-century English logician John Mill. According to John Mill, if the names given to objects convey information, that is, if they have a specific meaning, then they mean what they mean, not what they mean¹⁰.

In linguistics, there is a special term for the names of business objects - ergonims. It should be noted that the question of the place and position of the ergonomic dictionary in the language system is still the cause of scientific debate. Thus, D.A. Yalovets-Konovalova introduced the term "name of a commercial enterprise" as a category of ergonism and defined ergonism as a social association¹¹. According to R.I. Kozlov, ergonims do not always serve as names of economic associations, but are also associated with a specific place, the address of an enterprise, which allows them to be classified as toponyms¹².

⁸ Медведева Т.Н. Методические указания по курсу «История лингвистических учений» / Т.Н. Медведева. – Саратов, 2011. – 63 с. – http://elibrary.sgu.ru/uch_lit/456.pdf

⁹ Платон. Кратил // Платон. Собр. соч. в 4-х томах. – Том 1. – Москва: «Мысль», 1990. – с. 613– 682.

¹⁰ Рождественский Ю.В. Теория риторики / Ю.В. Рождественский. – Москва: Добросвет, 1997. – 597 с.

¹¹ Милль Дж. С. - Система логики. Том 1-2 (1865, 1867) <https://platona.net>.

¹² Яловец-Коновалова Д. А. Названия коммерческих предприятий: ономаσιологическая классификация и функционирование в современном русском языке: автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук: 10.02.01. – Челябинск: Челябинский ун-т. – 1997. – С.10. (24 с.)

Traditionally, ergonomics are divided into commercial (*shops, restaurants, cafes, hotels, etc.*) and non-commercial (*schools, universities, hospitals, hobby groups, etc.*). But at the moment, this division is losing its importance due to the transition of some non-commercial enterprises (for example, *language teaching centers, educational centers, medical centers*) to the commercial category.

Some researchers consider ergonomics in terms of three main functions: **nominative**, characteristic of all proper names; **information** and **advertising** that defines the specific functions of names intended for commercial activities. A number of works use a diachronic approach to the studied ergonomic units.

The onomastic system of any language, including the onomastic system of the Uzbek language, is extremely versatile in terms of quantity, huge in size, different from each other according to the nominative-functional characteristics, and at the same time, there is a certain connection with each other. Just as the lexical wealth of the language is made up of concrete lexical units, the onomastic fund of the language is made up of concrete proper nouns that are part of the onomastic lexicon. An onomastic unit actually refers to a concrete noun.

It is known that anthroponym (Greek: anthropos - anthropos + onoma-noun) is a personal name (name, surname, nickname, patronymic, etc.). One of the famous horse types¹³. A collection of proper nouns of all persons existing in a certain language is called anthroponymy. Anthroponymics or onomology is a branch of onomastics that studies the origin, development and functional characteristics of personal nouns (anthroponyms).

"The national uniqueness of Uzbek anthroponymy is ensured by two linguistic materials. These are: original Turkic names and Uzbek names. The national-linguistic spirit is especially evident in the creation of Uzbek names. Most of the names belonging to the original Turkic layer are names with a clearly perceptible appellative meaning. Nevertheless, in this layer of names, three different names can be found according to their meaning: 1) names whose meaning is clearly felt; 2) names whose meaning is now obscured; 3) names with dead meaning. Most Uzbek names belong to the first and second groups.

It is worth noting that because the English candidate was more influenced by existing traditions ("*Tesco*", "*Vendy's*", "*Sean's Bar*" pub, "*Angel & Royal*" English ergonomics did not undergo such serious changes depending on the historical period, due to the fact that they were more influenced by the hotel), English ergonomists have such a serious development depending on the historical period) and the superiority of the idea of business continuity from generation to generation (*Barnes & Noble*, *Crabtree & Evelyn*, *James Smith & Sons*, *Otterton Mill*).

It is worth noting that the English candidate has more influence on existing traditions ("*Tesco*", "*Wendy's*", pub "*Sean's Bar*", hotel "*Angel & Royal*") and the idea of business continuity from generation to generation. due to its superiority, English ergonomics did not undergo such serious changes depending on the historical period ("*Barnes & Noble*", "*Crabtree & Evelyn*", "*James Smith & Sons*", "*Otterton Mill*").

¹³ Begmatov E., Ulukov N. Explanatory dictionary of Uzbek onomastics terms. - Namangan, 2006. - B. 13.

Due to the rapid growth of ergonim nomination models, as well as methods aimed at increasing their pragmatism, it seems promising to further study ergonims as special units of onomastic space.

We have come to the conclusion that most ergonims are taken from the language in a pre-existing form, that is, common nouns have their own characteristics, and specific nouns are transonymized.

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